

Spatial, Kinetic and Potential Probability Distributions and Quantum Mechanics

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Newtonian mechanics focuses on $x(t)$ because physically one sees a particle move in space (i.e. through photons). As a result, it seems there is a focus on $P(x)dx$ in the sense of mapping each x to a dt value in the literature (1). Here we suggest that one may just as easily consider mapping each x to a $|p|$ or $pp/2m$ value. For a free particle, all of these distributions are uniform and impose a length in space (i.e. a length does not appear naturally unless one has a particle bouncing back and forth in a box.)

The reason that we suggest this is important is because $P(x)$, $P(|p|)$ and $P(pp/2m)$ do not distinguish between p and $-p$ (momenta). If one were to postulate a $P(p,x)$ and a $P(-p,x)$ and multiply these together, then $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = P(0, x)$. In other words, words one would not have any motion. Here 0 is the same as a $|p|$ value as it has no sign, but p and $-p$ have sign. We noted above that $P(pp/2m)$ and $P(|p|)$ are uniform, but there is a problem if one multiplies $P(|p|)P(|-p|)$ to try to describe $P(p,x)P(-p,x)$. In other words, these two products are not the same and only the latter suggests no motion. This, in turn, implies $P(p,x) = \exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$, which is one of the math solutions of $P(p,x)P(-p,x) = P(0, x)$ for $P(0,x) = 1/L$ if one wishes to have a non-growing probability in x . It seems that one cannot assign a uniform distribution to $P(p,x)$, $P(-p,x)$ if the sign is accounted for. This leads to a quantum mechanical viewpoint.

Classical Probability of Moving Particles

In (1) and other places in the literature, a dt associated with a fixed dx in a bound classical problem is said to be proportional to probability. Thus:

$$P(x)dx = Cdx/|v(x)| \quad \text{where } v(x) \text{ is velocity ((1))}$$

We argue that ((1)) is a special probability associated with mapping dx at x to a dt . One may just as well map x to $|p|$ (absolute value of momentum) or kinetic energy. The reason one maps to dt is that one is used to watching a particle move in space by bouncing photons off of it.

For a free particle, $P(x)dx = dx/L$, but

$$P(|p|,x) = dx/L \quad \text{and } P(pp/2m, x) = dx/L \quad ((2)) \quad \text{as well.}$$

One may immediately notice that $|p|$ and $pp/2m$ apply equally well to p and $-p$ (one dimension).

This leads to the question: What is $P(p,x)$ or $P(-p,x)$? Is it also a uniform distribution?

The Problem of $P(p,x)$, $P(-p,x)$ Representing Uniform Distributions

$$\text{If one considers } P(p,x)P(-p,x) = P(0,x) \quad ((3))$$

one has issues with $P(p,x)$ and $P(-p,x)$ being uniform because $p - p = 0$. 0 has no sign and fits $P(|p|,x)$, but $P(p,x)$ and $P(-p,x)$ have a sign which is important and should lead to a different solution.

Mathematically, there are two solutions to ((3)), namely a constant with no p , i.e. $1/L$ for $P(0,x)$ unnormalized or $\exp(ipx)$ for a non-growing probability.. The point seems to be that $\exp(ipx)$ retains information about the direction of p while still leading to a $P(0,x)=1/L$ if one uses $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$. In other words, $\exp(ipx)$ arises if one wishes to have a probability which retains information about the direction of p .

In a previous note which focused on information, we suggested that sign was a key piece of information which should be retained in some form of probability. Here we suggest a similar idea that one should not confuse $P(-p,x)$ with $P(|p|,x)$, even though there is a connection, namely:

$$P(-p,x)P(p,x) = P(|p|,x) \quad ((4))$$

In particular, $P(|p|,x)$ incorporates both p and $-p$ at the same time so to speak and such a view point would justify ((4)).

Furthermore, there is the issue of normalization. $P(|p|,x) = dx/L$ and is already normalized. Multiplying $P(|p|,x)P(|-p|,x)$ destroys normalization while ((4)) allows for $P(-p,x)=\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ multiplied by $\exp(ipx)/\sqrt{L}$ to create the correct normalization.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that using dt for fixed dx in a bound classical problem as being proportional to probability only gives one kind of probability, namely one focusing on x being mapped to dt . One may just easily map x to $|p|$ or $pp/2m$. In such a case, $P(x)dx=dx/L$ for all three mappings. Furthermore, p and $-p$ are accounted for. We ask, however, what is $P(-p,x)$ and $P(p,x)$? Should these also be uniform distributions? If one writes $P(-p,x)P(p,x)= P(0,x)$ and uses $P(0,x) = dx/L$ because there is no momentum direction for this value, then there are two math solutions, a constant and $\exp(ipx)$ for non increasing growth. We suggest that $P(|p|,x)$ incorporates p and $-p$ at the same time. Also p and $-p$ yielding 0 which has no sign is also another indicator that sign is not important for $p_{total}=0$, but is important for p and $-p$. Thus, we suggest that the probability form $\exp(ipx)$ should be taken seriously. We note that using $P(|p|,x)P(|-p|,x)$ leads to $1/L(1/L)$, but one does not have the same situation as p and $-p$ mapping to $p_{total}=0$.

Reference

1. Majernick, V. and Optarny, T. Entropic Uncertainty Relations for the Quantum Oscillator January 1999 Journal of Physics A Mathematical and General 29(9):2187 29(9):2187 DOI:10.1088/0305-4470/29/9/029 https://www.researchgate.net/publication/231048623_Entropic_uncertainty_relations_for_a_quantum_oscillator

